
DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF PROJECT E-ASE (ELECTRONIC AND AUTOMATED SCHOOL FORM FOR EDUCATORS) FOR SAN JOSE-LITEX SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

RADINO Q. PANGILINAN

Teacher II

San Jose-Litex Senior High School

sir.dinopangilinan@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the imperative for integrating technology to streamline administrative tasks in education has gained increasing recognition. Conventional paper-based methods for managing school forms often lead to inefficiencies, impeding the timely and accurate processing of critical information. The shift towards automated systems offers a promising solution to mitigate these challenges. By embracing automation, administrative burdens can be significantly reduced, allowing educators to redirect their focus towards student-centered activities and educational advancement.

This action research introduces the Electronic and Automated School Form (e-ASE), specifically designed to automate the processing of School Forms 9 and 10. Employing a descriptive research design, this study utilized a convenient sampling method to select participants based on researcher availability and preference. Data collection was conducted using a researcher-made questionnaire administered through Google Forms. Analysis involved the use of weighted mean and t-tests to assess functionality, efficiency, and design aspects.

Results demonstrate a high level of acceptance for the Automated School Form across functionality, efficiency, and design criteria. Statistical analysis indicates no significant difference

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

in the evaluation of its acceptability between two groups of respondents across these domains. These findings underscore the applicability of the research outcomes in the adoption and implementation of the Automated School Form.

Moreover, the study recommends promoting the adoption of the Automated School Form among educators and administrators to optimize the processing and storage of learner information and academic progress. The success of this initiative may also serve as a catalyst for other educational institutions to consider adopting similar automated solutions, thereby fostering broader improvements in administrative efficiency and educational quality.

Context and Rationale

Teaching, often regarded as a noble profession, is not without sacrifices, and time is among these sacrifices (Ancho & Bongco, 2019). Teachers must devote a tremendous amount of time and effort to their work. They are responsible for various tasks, such as creating lesson plans, marking homework, giving feedback, attending meetings and seminars, and participating in extracurricular activities. These duties may limit teachers' time, disrupting their work-life balance.

The launch of the **MATATAG**: Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa agenda by Vice President and Secretary of Education Sara Z. Duterte on January 30, 2023, is significant not only in terms of setting a new direction for the Department of Education (DepEd) but also in terms of addressing critical challenges in the education system.

The **MATATAG**: Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa agenda is focused on tackling a significant challenge in the education system: the heavy workload of teachers. Implementing the K-12 program and adopting modular and online learning approaches in response to the COVID-

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

INSTABRIGHT e-GAZETTE

ISSN: 2704-3010

Volume V, Issue III

February 2024

Available online at <https://www.instabrightgazette.com>

19 pandemic has increased the teacher workload. This has created a more challenging environment for teachers regarding lesson preparation and delivery. The agenda aims to address this issue by developing effective strategies to reduce teachers' workload, thus enabling them to deliver quality education to their students.

The Philippine public-school teachers play a vital role in the country's educational system, but they encounter various job challenges, including the demanding task of filling out school forms. These forms are necessary for monitoring student information, attendance, and academic progress, but manually completing them can be time-consuming and error-prone, resulting in delays and inaccurate data. This puts pressure on Filipino public-school teachers, who already have numerous responsibilities as educators, to allocate more time to complete these forms. This may lead to burnout, affecting the quality of education they provide. The excessive workload contributes to teacher burnout, depleting the teacher's physical and emotional energy (Malik, 2019).

When completing school forms, one of the critical concerns for San Jose-Litex Senior High School teachers is creating and using automated forms. These forms are typically required for public schools in Montalban Rizal. To address this issue, the proponent will develop and validate the project e-ASE (Electronic and Automated School Form for Educators), aiming to streamline administrative processes and tasks within school administration. The primary goal of this project is to assist educators in collecting, processing, and conveniently storing information, allowing them to focus their time and efforts on their teaching responsibilities.

There are many reasons why creating automated school forms is a must not only at public schools but also at some government agencies in the country. According to REPUBLIC ACT NO. 11927, July 30, 2022, Also Known As *AN ACT TO ENHANCE THE PHILIPPINE DIGITAL WORKFORCE COMPETITIVENESS, ESTABLISHING FOR PURPOSE AN INTER-AGENCY COUNCIL*

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban, Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

INSTABRIGHT e-GAZETTE

ISSN: 2704-3010

Volume V, Issue III

February 2024

Available online at <https://www.instabrightgazette.com>

FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND COMPETITIVENESS OF THE PHILIPPINE DIGITAL WORKFORCE AND OTHER PURPOSES; this is why government schools such as San Jose –Litex Senior High School must adapt and engage in this automation of school forms, especially since there has been a need for an efficient and more reliable system for managing student information. Moreover, manual forms and paper-based processes require much more budget, are time-consuming and prone to human errors, which can cause the teachers to collect the information they need inaccurately.

The Division of Rizal under the Department of Education in the Philippines consistently advocates for the automation of school forms to enhance the gathering and administration of student data, given that digital formats are readily accessible. This approach could be integrated with other educational institutions in Montalban Rizal. Senior High School administration will benefit from increased efficiency, effectiveness, and user-friendliness. Ultimately, this initiative will enable educators to concentrate on delivering quality education to their students.

The primary objective of this study is to examine the existing form-handling process and the technical prerequisites for the automation of school forms. The investigation will also consider such a system's anticipated benefits and limitations, particularly in San Jose-Litex Senior High School and other public schools within Montalban, Rizal. The findings of this research will offer crucial insights into the potential advantages of form automation, which can serve as a blueprint for future endeavors to leverage technology to enhance the education system.

Action Research Questions

This research study sought to determine the efficacy of the automated school form in inputting learners' scholastic reports of San Jose Litex Senior High School.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

It specifically sought to answer the following:

1. What is the level of acceptability of Automated School Form as perceived by Class Advisers and ICT Teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Usability;
 - 1.2 Functionality;
 - 1.3 Design?

2. Are there any significant differences in the levels of acceptability on the developed Automated School form as perceived by the Class Advisers and ICT Teacher concerning the above criteria?

Action Research Methods

A. Participants and other Sources of Data and Information

Project e-ASE seeks to establish a highly systematic and organized framework for recording and monitoring learners' progress. Its main goal is to ensure that the data collected is reliable and accurate by relying on all stakeholders' expertise in teaching-learning.

To achieve this, the project will leverage the knowledge and experience of the 3-ICT Coordinators within the Public Senior High Schools and 46 teacher-advisers currently handling advisory classes at San Jose-Litex Senior High School in Montalban, Rizal, for the School Year 2023-2024. By engaging all those involved in the teaching-learning process, the project will benefit from a vast pool of insights and perspectives that will ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

The project will use purposive sampling, a highly targeted sampling approach that selects participants based on specific criteria to facilitate data collection. By utilizing this approach, the project proponent can ensure that the teacher-advisers best suited to provide the necessary information are included in the data collection process.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The data was collected using a researcher-made questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. Respondents received the survey link through email and messenger.

The questionnaire evaluated the acceptability of the developed Automated School Form based on functionality, efficiency, and design.

The following scale, range, and verbal interpretation was used to measure the efficiency level as perceived by the respondents.

SCALE	RANGE	VERBAL INTERPRETATION
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very Much Accepted
4	3.41 – 4.20	Much Accepted
3	2.61 – 3.40	Accepted
2	1.80 – 2.60	Moderately Accepted
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Accepted

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

C. Data Analysis Plan

A quantitative research method will be employed to analyze the data collected for this research proposal. The study aims to validate the project's functionality, efficiency, and design using appropriate validation tools. The study's results will be gathered, interpreted, and analyzed using statistical tools like mean and t-tests to address the research problems.

Specifically, the mean will be used to determine the level of acceptability of automated school forms among the participants. This will involve computing the average score of the responses obtained from the survey questionnaire administered to the participants. Additionally, the t-test will be employed to compare the mean scores of different groups of participants to ascertain if there are significant differences in their perceptions of the use of automated school forms.

Using these statistical tools will enable us to draw meaningful conclusions from the data and make informed decisions regarding project implementation. Furthermore, the findings from this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge in the field and inform future research in educational technology.

Discussion of Results and Recommendations

This part of the study presents the results and recommendations based on the evaluation of the Developed Automated School Form's acceptability by Advisers and ICT teachers. Furthermore, it explores the significant differences observed between these groups in their evaluations of the system's functionality, efficiency, design level.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

Table 1. Acceptability of Automated School Form by Functionality

FUNCTIONALITY	ADVISERS		ICT TEACHERS	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
Data Accuracy	4.22	VMA	4.67	VMA
User-Friendliness	4.35	VMA	5.00	VMA
Performance	4.52	VMA	4.33	VMA
Scalability	4.33	VMA	4.33	VMA
Print Customization	4.20	MA	4.33	VMA
Print Preview	4.52	VMA	5.00	VMA
	4.36	VMA	4.61	VMA

Note: 1.00 – 1.79 Not Accepted (NA); 1.80 – 2.60 Moderately Accepted (MLA); 2.61 – 3.40 Accepted (A); 3.41 – 4.20 Much Accepted (MA); 4.21 – 5.00 (VMA)

Table 1 demonstrates the acceptability of the Automated School Form in processing various inputs, specifically student personal information, grades, attendance for the SF9 report card, and Form-137 (SF10), as perceived by advisers and ICT teachers. The evaluation by the respondents indicates a high level of acceptance across six indicators. Advisers rated the functionality with an average weighted mean of 4.36, while ICT teachers rated it 4.61. These

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

ratings suggest that the developed automated school form excels in data accuracy, user-friendliness, performance, scalability, print customization, and print preview capabilities.

Table 2. Acceptability of Automated School Form by Efficiency

EFFICIENCY	ADVISERS		ICT TEACHERS	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
Resource Usage	4.32	VMA	5.00	VMA
Data Processing Speed	4.35	VMA	4.67	VMA
File Size	4.41	VMA	4.00	VMA
Memory Management	4.37	VMA	4.67	VMA
Automation	4.46	VMA	5.00	VMA
	4.38	VMA	4.67	VMA

Note: 1.00 – 1.79 Not Accepted (NA); 1.80 – 2.60 Moderately Accepted (MLA); 2.61 – 3.40 Accepted (A); 3.41 – 4.20 Much Accepted (MA); 4.21 – 5.00 (VMA)

Table 2 illustrates the acceptability of the Automated School Form concerning efficiency, focusing on indicators such as Resource Usage, Data Processing Speed, File Size, Memory Management, and Automation, as perceived by advisers and ICT teachers. The advisers rated these aspects with an average weighted mean of 4.38, while ICT teachers rated them 4.67. These ratings indicate a high level of acceptance with the efficiency of the developed automated school form. The system performs well in terms of resource utilization, data processing speed, file size

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

management, memory efficiency, and automation capabilities, as acknowledged by both advisers and ICT teachers.

Table 3. Acceptability of Automated School Form by Design

DESIGN	ADVISERS		ICT TEACHERS	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
User Interface Design	4.43	VMA	5.00	VMA
Layout and Organization	4.59	VMA	5.00	VMA
Color and Typography	4.46	VMA	4.67	VMA
Accessibility	4.46	VMA	4.33	VMA
	4.49	VMA	4.75	VMA

Note: 1.00 – 1.79 Not Accepted (NA); 1.80 – 2.60 Moderately Accepted (MLA); 2.61 – 3.40 Accepted (A); 3.41 – 4.20 Much Accepted (MA); 4.21 – 5.00 (VMA)

Table 3 presents the acceptability of the Automated School Form based on its design aspects, specifically User Interface Design, Layout and Organization, Color and Typography, and Accessibility, as perceived by advisers and ICT teachers. Advisers rated these design indicators with an average weighted mean of 4.49, while ICT teachers rated them 4.75. These evaluations indicate a very high level of acceptance regarding the design quality of the developed automated school form.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

The system's design is highly regarded for its user interface, which includes intuitive navigation and functionality. The layout and organization of information are well-structured, enhancing usability and accessibility. Additionally, the use of color and typography is effective in facilitating user interaction and readability. Moreover, the form's accessibility features are robust, ensuring inclusivity and ease of use for all users.

In summary, both advisers and ICT teachers agree that the design of the automated school form excels in terms of User Interface Design, Layout and Organization, Color and Typography, and Accessibility, highlighting its effectiveness in supporting educational processes.

Table 4. Significant Difference between the Evaluation on the Functionality Level of Automated School Form as revealed by the two groups of respondents

FUNCTIONALITY	Mean	SD	T-test	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Advisers	4.36	0.14	1.73	0.1136	Accept HO	Not Significant
ICT Teachers	4.61	0.33				

Table 4 illustrates the comparison of evaluations regarding the functionality of the Automated School Form between two groups. The computed p-value of 0.1136 exceeds the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is accepted. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the acceptability levels between advisers and ICT teachers concerning the functionality of the Automated School Form.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

Table 5. Significant Difference between the Evaluation on the Efficiency Level of Automated School Form as revealed by the two groups of respondents

EFFICIENCY	Mean	SD	T-test	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Advisers	4.38	0.05	1.57	0.1591	Accept HO	Not Significant
ICT Teachers	4.67	0.41				

Table 5 presents a comparison of evaluations on the efficiency of the Automated School Form between two groups. The computed p-value of 0.1591 exceeds the predetermined significance level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no statistically significant difference in the acceptability levels between advisers and ICT teachers regarding the efficiency of the Automated School Form.

Table 6. Significant Difference between the Evaluation on the Design Level of Automated School Form as revealed by the two groups of respondents

DESIGN	Mean	SD	T-test	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Advisers	4.49	0.07	1.16	0.1574	Accept HO	Not Significant
ICT Teachers	4.75	0.32				

Table 6 shows a comparison of assessments regarding the design of the Automated School Form between two groups. The calculated p-value of 0.1574 is higher than the predefined

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

significance level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, suggesting that there is no statistically significant distinction in the perceived acceptability of the Automated School Form's design between advisers and ICT teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were arrived.

1. The developed Automated School Form for Senior High School is Very Much Accepted in terms of Functionality, Efficiency, and its design.
2. There is no significant difference between the evaluation in terms of Functionality, Efficiency, and its design as revealed by the two groups of respondents.

Recommendations

From the light of the conclusion drawn from this study, the following recommendations are presented.

1. The school may be utilized the developed Automated School Form in processing and storing learner's information including the learner's personal information, grades, attendance record that are necessary in accomplishing School Form 9 and 10.
2. Other schools may be encouraged to benchmark and adapt the developed Automated School Form for Senior High School.
3. Future developers may use the developed Automated School Form for Senior High School. and could enhance more from their future research and development.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

INSTABRIGHT e-GAZETTE

ISSN: 2704-3010

Volume V, Issue III

February 2024

Available online at <https://www.instabrightgazette.com>

REFERENCES:

Bongco, Roxanne & Ancho, Inero. (2019). Exploring Filipino Teachers' Professional Workload. 9. 19-29. 10.37134/jrpptte.vol9.no2.2.2019.

Congress of the Philippines. (2022). Republic Act No. 11927, *An Act to Enhance the Philippine Digital Workforce Competitiveness, Establish the Purpose of an Inter-Agency Council for the Development and Competitiveness of the Digital Philippine Workforce, and Other Purposes.* Retrieved from https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2022/ra_11927_2022.html

Department of Education. (2023, January 30). Matatag: DepEd's New Agenda To Resolve Basic Education Woes. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2023/01/30/matatag-depeds-new-agenda-to-resolve-basic-education-woes/>

Malik, Amina & Singh, Parbudyal. (2019). The role of employee attributions in burnout of "talented" employees. *Personnel Review.* ahead-of-print. 10.1108/PR-02-2018-0064.

Nacional, R. (2022). Philippine Public Senior High School Time Optimization of School Forms Preparation. *American Journal of Education and Technology.* 1. 29–35. 10.54536/ajet.v1i2.464.

Nicodemus, J.T. (n.d.). Automation: The Future of School Forms. Department of Education. The Schools Division Office Science City of Muñoz. Retrieved from <http://www.depedscm.com/automation-the-future-of-schoolforms/?fbclid=IwAR2ni9ZUjQAKu6LdBdUp7NIK0W53kkRhcULINiRAewELugQHmGI dQGb1Jtg>

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez, Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto

INSTABRIGHT e-GAZETTE

ISSN: 2704-3010

Volume V, Issue III

February 2024

Available online at <https://www.instabrightgazette.com>

Villarejo, Floralyn & Mamburao, Ruben & Lumapenet, Husna. (2022). Work Demands and Occupational Burnout among Public School Teachers in The Philippines. International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education. 8. 4926-4926.

Editorial Team

Editor-in-Chief: Alvin B. Punongbayan

Associate Editor: Andro M. Bautista

Managing Editor: Raymart O. Basco

Web Editor: Nikko C. Panotes

Manuscript Editors / Reviewers:

Chin Wen Cong, Christopher DC. Francisco, Camille P. Alicaway, Pinky Jane A. Perez,
Mary Jane B. Custodio, Irene H. Andino, Mark-Jhon R. Prestoza, Keive O. Casimiro, Ma. Rhoda E. Panganiban
Rjay C. Calaguas, Mario A. Cudiamat, Jesson L. Hero, Albert Bulawat, Cris T. Zita, Allan M. Manaloto
